

Status of Devolution of Functions to Panchayats: An Analysis of Mapping of Functions in Bihar Since 73rd Constitutional Amendment Act, 1992

Paper Id : 20724 Submission Date : 2025-09-09 Acceptance Date : 2025-09-21 Publication Date : 2025-09-25

This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.17365214

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/remarking.php#8>

Amit Kumar
Research Scholar
Department Of Political
Science
Christ Church College
Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh,
India

Ashutosh Saxena
Research Supervisor
Department Of Political
Science
CSJM University
Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh,
India

Abstract

The 73rd Constitutional Amendment Act, 1992, mandated the devolution of powers to Panchayati Raj Institutions (PRIs) in India. Bihar, like other states, has made efforts to devolve functions to PRIs. Local governments, world over, big or small, shape daily life for their residents. In India, Panchayats, the grassroots local bodies, handle essential civic duties like sanitation, waste disposal, primary healthcare and education, drinking-water supply, and registering births and deaths. Since these bodies are very close to the people, their decisions have a direct impact on the quality of life of the local residents. Following the principle of subsidiarity, the idea that tasks should be managed by the smallest competent authority, many States have formally devolved a broad set of responsibilities to Panchayats. However, this often happens without granting them matching authority or resources. As a result, Panchayat leaders and local citizens end up frustrated and dissatisfied. This paper examines the status of devolution of powers to PRIs, with a focus on the mapping of functions to PRIs in Bihar. The paper analyses the extent of devolution, the functions devolved, and the challenges faced by PRIs in implementing these functions. The paper concludes that while Bihar has made progress in devolving functions to PRIs, there are still significant challenges to be addressed.

Keywords

Panchayati Raj Institutions, Devolution, Mapping of Functions, Decentralisation.

Introduction

The concept of devolution of functions to PRIs in India gained constitutional recognition with the 73rd Amendment Act of 1992, which mandated the establishment of a three-tier system of local governance across rural India. The literature on this subject reflects both the potential of decentralized governance and the persistent challenges in operationalizing devolution in its true spirit. A foundational study by Manor (1999) emphasizes the distinction between decentralization and devolution. While decentralization can include mere delegation or de-concentration, devolution refers to the transfer of real authority, responsibilities, and resources to local bodies. Manor argues that although Indian states were constitutionally mandated to devolve powers to PRIs, the political and bureaucratic reluctance to cede control has limited meaningful devolution.

Objective of study

This paper examines the status of devolution of powers to PRIs, with a focus on the mapping of functions to PRIs in Bihar. The paper analyses the extent of devolution, the functions devolved, and the challenges faced by PRIs in implementing these functions.

Review of Literature

An analysis of the post-amendment period reveals that although most states formally transferred functions to PRIs, there is wide variation in the extent and quality of devolution. Many states have transferred functions without transferring the corresponding functionaries or funds. This "empty devolution," undermines the autonomy and effectiveness of PRIs (Mathew and Buch, 2000). The Planning Commission (2006) report on local governance noted that activity mapping, an exercise aimed at clarifying the roles of different tiers of panchayats, has been carried out unevenly across states. The report also highlights that the failure to institutionalize planning processes at the grassroots level, particularly the preparation of Gram Panchayat Development Plans (GPDPs) has further constrained the potential of devolution. The "3Fs" (Functions, Functionaries, and Finances) are very important in assessing the success of devolution. The devolution must be comprehensive and simultaneous across all three dimensions to empower Panchayats meaningfully. In the state-wise comparative analysis, Kerala and Karnataka emerged as relatively successful examples, whereas states like Bihar and Uttar Pradesh lag due to weak political will and administrative

inertia (Oommen, 2005). There is a need for community involvement through active Gram Sabhas. For the devolution to be democratic, local citizens must be empowered to hold Panchayats accountable (Tandon & Mohanty, 2018).

Although more than three decades have passed since the implementation of the 73rd Constitutional Amendment Act, substantial progress is still lacking. The transfer of financial and administrative authority to panchayats remains largely unfulfilled. While a few states have initiated this process, many are yet to take meaningful action. In several cases, responsibilities have been assigned without the accompanying transfer of staff or financial resources. There is an urgent need to overhaul the election infrastructure, audit systems, and finance commissions at the state level to bring them in line with their central counterparts. Moreover, Gram Sabhas must be granted real authority to supervise and monitor the functioning of Gram Panchayats (Ramachentrayar & Ram, 2025).

Main Text

Functions of Panchayats in Bihar

After comparing the functions assigned to the PRIs under the Constitution and the Bihar Panchayati Raj Act, 2006 (BPRA, 2006), it is found that BPRA, 2006 includes all functions listed in the Eleventh Schedule of the Constitution. These functions are provided under Section 22 for Gram Panchayats (GP), Section 47 for Panchayat Samitis (PS), Section 73 for Zila Parishads (ZP) and Section 96 to 122 for Gram Kacheris (GK).

These rural local bodies mainly perform four types of functions as listed below:

Regulatory Functions: Issuing Death & Birth Certificate, Trade license and other Regulations, etc. besides judicial functions through the GKs.

Planning Functions: Schemes for both economic development and social justice.

Civic Functions: Water Supply, Sanitation, Drainage, Sewerage, Solid Waste Management, Street Lighting, Streets and Footpaths, Parks, Playgrounds, Burial and Cremation Grounds, Library, Museum etc.

Agency Functions: Functions assigned under the Central and State Schemes and policies.

Need for Activity Mapping

Mapping of activities is a critical first step before transferring responsibilities to PRIs. It clarifies who does what at each PRI tier, eliminating overlap and confusion. This isn't a one-off task, it needs to be revisited regularly, especially when designing local socio-economic programs, reorganizing institutions, or drafting relevant laws.

The key aspects of activity mapping include

Breaking down broad sectors (like education, health, sanitation) into specific services and sub-activities (e.g., monitoring teacher attendance, maintaining school infrastructure),

Assigning each activity to the appropriate PRI level or government department, following principles of subsidiarity, public accountability, and financial clarity.

Embedding this practice into policy and budgets, ensuring alignment between activity allocation and funding, so PRIs receive clear financial backing aligned with their responsibilities. By institutionalizing periodic reviews and aligning activity mapping with legislation, organizational structures, and fiscal planning, PRIs can deliver services more transparently, efficiently, and responsively at the local level.

Methodology

The present study is mainly based on secondary data derived from the published reports of Ministry of Panchayati Raj (MoPR), Bihar State Finance Commission, etc., related to devolution to panchayats in India. The study also uses the other literature on the devolution to panchayats. In this study, the researcher has utilised the available information and data to conduct a critical evaluation. The study is qualitative in nature. The research design adopted in the study is analytical in nature, mainly focusing on the status and challenges in devolution to panchayats in Bihar.

Analysis

Devolution of Functions to Panchayats in Bihar: Current Status

To empower Panchayati Raj Institutions (PRIs) as truly effective local governments, it is essential that they be granted authority over the responsibilities enshrined in the Constitution. The functions currently performed by the State Government bodies must be shifted to PRIs. This requires breaking down each function into discrete activities and allocating these individual

activities based on principles of public finance, accountability, and sound governance to either of the appropriate level of PRI or relevant government official. This allocation should follow core principles such as subsidiarity i.e., devolving tasks to the most local appropriate level, democratic decentralization i.e., transferring genuine administrative, financial, and political power), and citizen-centricity i.e., prioritizing transparency, participation, and responsiveness to community needs (SFC Bihar,2006).

The extent of the powers devolved to panchayats in India vary significantly across the states. The situation is far from satisfactory in most of the states. The Government of India has been continuously handholding states in devolving powers to panchayats as mentioned in the Constitution and creating a framework for accountability, transparency and efficiency (Devolution Report, 2024). A few studies conducted on the devolution of powers to PRIs in India have highlighted the challenges faced by these institutions. The devolution of powers to PRIs has been very slow and incomplete (Kumar, 2013). It has been argued that the lack of capacity and resources has hindered the effective functioning of PRIs (Singh, 2015). These studies highlight the need for a more nuanced understanding of the devolution of powers to PRIs in Bihar.

The present status of devolution of “3Fs” is presented in Table 3.

Table 4.: Status of Devolution of 3 Fs to Panchayats in Bihar

Funds	Functions	Functionaries
<p>SFC5: No taxes are collected by the PRIs but a proposal regarding the same is under consideration of state government.</p> <p>SFC6 Observation: While the BPRAs 2006 has conferred powers of taxation on PRIs, they are awaiting guidelines from PRD, which is still awaiting approval of Govt.</p>	<p>SFC5: Activity mapping has been conducted. 20 depts. have issued GOs.</p> <p>SFC6 Observation: Activity mapping orders have issued, but not acted upon. Funds for transferred functions are still being allocated to administrative departments.</p>	<p>SFC5: Departmental staffs are answerable to departments. Anganwadi workers, health workers and teachers are appointed by PRIs.</p> <p>SFC6 Observation: The workers mentioned above are appointed by PRIs but do not report to them. Departments that have issued activity mapping orders, have not transferred services of officers handling those activities to PRIs.</p>

Source: SFC6, Bihar

Note: - **SFC:** State Finance Commission; **3 Fs:** Funds, Functions and Functionaries; **GOs:** Government Orders

1. Status of Activity Mapping of Functions in Bihar

The 73rd Constitutional Amendment Act, 1992, marked a significant shift in India's governance paradigm. The Act mandated the devolution of powers to PRIs, with the aim of promoting decentralized governance and participatory development. Bihar, like other states, has made efforts to devolve functions to PRIs. However, the extent and effectiveness of this devolution remain unclear.

An empirical study in Bihar reveals that while the state has issued notifications for transferring functions from 20 departments to PRIs, actual implementation remains patchy. Functionaries often remain under the control of line departments, and Panchayats lack the fiscal autonomy to carry out even basic functions. The lack of capacity-building initiatives, poor audit systems, and ineffective Gram Sabhas further limit devolution (Singh and Sharma, 2013). As per the Panchayati Raj Department of Bihar, 20 departments have transferred 79 functions to the Gram Panchayats, 60 functions to the Panchayat Samitis and 61 functions to the Zila Parishads. Although the figures might look substantial, in practice, the transfer of functions has been more akin to “delegation”, where state authorities retain control rather than true “devolution”, which involves handing over genuine power, responsibility, and resources. Many departments like Agriculture, Revenue, Water Resources, Education, Health, Animal Husbandry, Forests, Rural Development, Energy, Social Welfare, Public Distribution, and others have nominally transferred functions, but they have not ceded meaningful authority or budget autonomy. In reality, this activity mapping has had little impact. Funds for these transferred functions are not directly routed to the local institutions; instead, the originating departments continue to receive and control the budgets for these services. Essentially, local bodies have gotten the duties without the fiscal independence to carry them out illustrative of “delegation without devolution”.

While the figures might appear encouraging, the 15th Central Finance Commission report shows that in Bihar, only 17 out of the 29 functions listed in the Eleventh Schedule have been officially transferred to PRIs. Both the 5th State

Finance Commission and the Comptroller and Auditor General (CAG) stress that these transfers resemble delegation rather than genuine devolution, as PRIs lack meaningful authority and adequate resources. Departments that have handed over responsibilities include Agriculture, Revenue and Land Development, Water Resources (specifically minor irrigation), Animal Husbandry, Fisheries, Forest and Environment, Industry, Public Health Engineering, Rural Development, Rural Engineering, Energy, Primary and Adult Education, Literacy, Cultural Activities, Medical and Family Welfare, Social Welfare, Services for the Disabled, Public Distribution, and Disaster Relief. Despite this, only six functions, drinking water, rural roads, renewable energy, poverty reduction programs, education, and upkeep of community assets—are actually implemented by Gram Panchayats, according to the 2020 CAG Audit Report. The 5th State Finance Commission further notes that 20 departments have issued Government Orders (GOs) based on Ministry of Panchayati Raj (MoPR) 2012 guidelines. However, the department and subject-wise progress on activity mapping remains poor. For Panchayats to operate efficiently across all levels, it is essential that they have a clear understanding of their roles and responsibilities, underscoring the importance of completing and communicating activity mapping to these bodies (Krishnakumar, Bareddy & Srivastava, 2023).

There is a provision in the Constitution of India for the functions to be performed by the PRIs. The Eleventh Schedule of the Constitution contains a list of 29 functions which can assigned to PRIs by the respective state legislatures by passing an enabling provision. The below table details about the number of activities being performed by different tiers of PRIs.

Table Devolution of functions by 20 departments to the 3 tiers of PRIs in Bihar

S. No	Departments	No. of activities transferred to PRIs		
		GP	PS	ZP
1	Agriculture	4	6	6
2	Revenue and Land Development	10	1	-
3	Water Resources (Minor Irrigation)	8	3	2
4	Animal Husbandry and Fishery	10	3	8
5	Forest and Environment	5	5	5
6	Industry	6	6	6
7	Public Health Engineering	3	3	4
8	Rural development	3	2	1
9	Rural Engineering (Road, Bridge, Culvert, etc.)	1	1	2
10	Energy	3	3	3
11	Primary Education	9	8	7
12	Adult Education	1	1	1
13	Literacy	1	1	1
14	Cultural Activities	3	2	3
15	Medical	1	1	-
16	Family Welfare	1	1	-
17	Social Welfare	5	5	5
18	Welfare of Handicapped	2	4	4
19	Public Distribution System	2	3	3
20	Relief and Rehabilitation	1	1	-
Total		79	60	61

Source: CAG Report, 2020

All the 29 functions mentioned in the Eleventh Schedule have been broken down into various small activities to be assigned to the most appropriate level of PRIs. Out of which the 20 departments in Bihar have devolved 79 activities to GPs, 60 activities to PSs and 61 activities to ZPs.

Status of Regulatory Functions

The present status of regulatory functions is presented in Table 5.2.

Table 5.2: Status of Regulatory Functions

Activity	Status
Issuing Death & Birth Certificate	Functioning at GP level.
Trade license and other Regulations	No activity at any of the three levels.
Judicial functions through GK	GKs (8387) are functional in all GPs. Services of Office Secretary and Nyaya Mitra have been made available to assist the Sarpanch. Funds to meet office Expenses of GK are given out of SFC Grant.

Source: SFC6, Bihar
Status of Civic Functions

The present status of regulatory functions is presented in Table 5.3.

Table 5.3: Status of Civic Functions

Activity	Status
Solid Waste management	No activity
Sanitation	Other than construction of drains, no other activity
Street lighting	No activity
Parks/Playgrounds	No activity
Burial /Cremation grounds	Functioning well at all levels.
Library/Museum	No activity at the GP & PS. Limited activity at the ZP.

Source: SFC6, Bihar
Status of Planning Functions

District Planning Committee: Article 243ZD of the Constitution envisages formation of a District Planning Committee (DPC) to consolidate the plans prepared by both the Panchayats and the Municipalities in the district and to prepare a draft development plan for the district as a whole.

During the five-year period from 2015 to 2020, the PRIs have carried out two Saat Nishchaya Schemes 'Mukhya Mantri Gramin Peya Jal Yojna' and 'Mukhya Mantri Gramin Naali Gali Yojna' using the SFC transfers and State funds. Every GP has been involved in their implementation. This task involved performance of planning functions, such as need assessment, formulation of individual schemes, their scrutiny and approval, supervision of construction and monitoring of progress. The process followed by the PRIs to execute the schemes is explained below:

1. Scheme selection was done by a Ward Level Implementation and Monitoring Committee in the backdrop of baseline survey conducted under the supervision of District Level Committee.
2. Technical approval was granted by the Block Level Committee.
3. Administrative approval of schemes was done by the GP.

The Block and District level Committees monitored and reviewed implementation and progress.

Status of Agency Functions

The panchayats in India perform of a number of functions assigned under the Central and State Schemes and policies. As these local bodies are the nearest to the people, they play an important role in the success of central as well as state government schemes and programmes.

The panchayats play an active part in the scheme implementation by identification of the suitable schemes under MGNREGA, Saat Nishyay Programme, Swachh Bharat Mission. The other functions include the identification and verification of beneficiaries eligible and in actual need under these schemes.

Findings

1. A total Of 79 functions at GP level, 60 functions at PS and 61 functions at ZS level have been transferred by 20 department of the Government of Bihar, but these are mere a delegation of functions rather than devolution as the departments continue to receive budgetary allocation in respect of those functions transferred to PRIs. The extent of the transfer of these functions also varies across departments.
2. Some of the regulatory functions like issuing birth and death certificates are being performed well at GP level as well as Gram Kachhehary are also functional at the GP level.
3. In respect of agency functions panchayats play an important role in the proper implementation of schemes of centre as well states including identification of works as well as scheme beneficiaries. Every GP has been involved in their implementation. This task involved performance of planning functions, such as need assessment, formulation of individual schemes, their

scrutiny and approval, supervision of construction and monitoring of progress.

4. The civic functions performed by the panchayats include construction of drainage, maintenance of burial grounds. The maintenance of library/Museum is being done at ZP level.

Conclusion

There is a consistent gap between the constitutional vision of democratic decentralization and the ground realities of implementation. The reluctance of state governments to relinquish control, the lack of administrative and financial support, and poor capacity-building continue to hinder effective devolution. Strengthening institutional frameworks, empowering Gram Sabhas, and fostering political commitment are essential steps toward realizing the full potential of the 73rd Amendment. The study concludes that while Bihar has made significant progress in devolving functions to PRIs, there are still significant challenges to be addressed. The state government needs to strengthen the capacity of PRIs, provide adequate funding, and ensure transparency and accountability.

References

1. Krishnakumar, D., Bareddy, P. & Srivastava, S. (2023). *Report on Legal framework and Status of Devolution in Bihar*. Anode Governance Lab. Bangalore
2. Kumar, A. (2013). *Decentralization and Participatory Governance in India*. *Journal of Asian Public Policy*, 6(2), 147-162.
3. Manor, J. (1999). *The Political Economy of Democratic Decentralization*. The World Bank.
4. Mathew, G., & Buch, N. (2000). *Status of Panchayati Raj in the States and Union Territories of India 2000*. Institute of Social Sciences.
5. Ministry of Panchayati Raj (MoPR). (2024). *Status of Devolution to Panchayats in States*
6. Oommen, M. A. (2005). *Devolution of Resources to Rural Local Bodies in India: State Practices*. Institute of Social Sciences.
7. Oommen, M. A. (2009). *Limits of a Devolution Index*. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 44(29), 17-21.
8. Planning Commission. (2006). *Report of the Working Group on Decentralised Planning and Panchayati Raj Institutions for the Eleventh Five Year Plan (2007–2012)*. Government of India.
9. Ramachentrayar, P. & Ram, G. (2025). *A Study on Financial Performance of Panchayati Raj Institutions in Andaman & Nicobar Islands*. Thiagarajar College of Preceptors Edu Spectra. 7. 1-10.
10. Singh, R. (2015). *Panchayati Raj in India: A Critical Analysis*. *Journal of Rural Development*, 34(1), 1-18.
11. Singh, R., & Sharma, A. (2013). *Devolution of Powers to Panchayats in Bihar: A Reality Check*. *Indian Journal of Public Administration*, 59(3), 481–498.
12. Tandon, R., & Mohanty, R. (2018). *Strengthening Participatory Local Governance: Lessons from the Field*. *Participatory Research in Asia (PRIA)*.